

SHADOW OF DIGITAL ECONOMICS

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this article is to analyze, discuss, and develop an approach to defining the shadow digital economy that accompanies worldwide digitalization processes. Digital economy implies total globalization, creates an ultra-high competitive environment, provides a new quality of life, business and public services. At the same time, many traditional areas of activity are being destroyed. In addition to understandable achievements, it is necessary to analyze new obvious and hidden threats that digitalization processes carry. An analysis of the causes and factors of the emergence and functioning of the new segment in the shadow economy is conducted. The approaches to the definition of this category and its content are discussed. A classification of criminal-oriented products and services that are the basis of a highly profitable illegal business has been proposed. The problem of confrontation with Shadow Digital Economics acquires particular urgency in the face of the emergence of new overt and hidden threats to the individuals, society and the state.

1. Introduction

The shadow economy, which appeared during the formation of commodity-money relations, remains one of the most burning issues for developed and developing countries. Regularly announced measures and means to combat the shadow economy do not produce effective results, unfortunately. It should be noted that the basis of any human activity is information that characterizes many aspects of the creative, production and marketing processes. Information acts as an object of claims down to criminal ones, has existed since ancient times as a subject of exchange and sale, and the role and relevance of information in government and society management is on a constant and consistent rise.

Building an information society has led to an increase in the need for a variety of information that characterizes virtually all aspects of the activities of the individual, society and the state. Simultaneously with these processes, an increase in the volume of illegal activities in relation to the information itself, the processes of its receipt and transmission via communication channels, places of concentration and storage of information resources is noted. In other words, the extraction of information in all its forms, through the use of various products and services, has turned into a highly profitable illegal business for a group of entrepreneurs.

The authors of the famous and popular book "The Age of Cryptocurrency: How Bitcoin and the Blockchain Are Challenging the Global Economic Order" note that society itself is changing rapidly and

continuously. "Digital technologies and online computing are at the epicenter of these changes, transforming the principles of the organization of society, public relations and business connections, because all aspects of our lives increasingly depend on the power of computers and network communications".

2. Literature Review

Interest in the shadow processes in the economy arose relatively recently. The results of separate isolated studies led to the formation of a new scientific direction in the economy, and a multitude of international and national programs at the state level began to be developed in order to counteract the processes of the shadow economy and remove them from the shadows. Special attention should be directed at the works of the Austrian scientist Friedrich Schneider, which reflect all aspects of the problems of the shadow economy, not only in developed but also in developing countries.

The first mention of the category "shadow information economy" in the post-Soviet space was made in the work of R. Gilyarevsky. The complex of studies conducted by Shneider F, in collaboration with other scientists, allowed developing theoretical approaches to the definition of the category of the shadow economy, the types of taxonomy of underground economic activity. This research direction received further development in subsequent publications related to:

- development of issues of consumer attitudes to the processes of shadow information activities, determining factors for the shadow economy of

Eurozone member countries with the development of a MIMIC model,

- identification of the economic and demographic characteristics of the subjects of the digital shadow economy,
- vulnerability market analysis,
- Shadow IT Evaluation Model,
- crimeware business models and cybercrime development,
- global average cost of cybercrime.

Publications of the RAND corporation deserve a special mention.

An analysis of the available publications allowed us to suggest filling the category of TPE from several points of view, including organizational, technological, etc.

3. Research Methodology

The methodology of this research is based on a systematic approach, which includes the formation of a concept and statement of tasks, the collection of statistical information from available sources (scientific and monographic literature, reports of research companies specializing in the field of information security and its economic aspects), processing and analysis of the collected information using game theory, econometric analysis and modeling.

One of the first tasks that were set by the authors was to analyze such categories as the shadow, unobservable, criminal economy, etc. The starting point should be to accept and consider the methodology proposed by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and discussed in some publications. In particular, the following categories are distinguished:

- Underground production: activities that are productive and legal but are deliberately concealed from public authorities to avoid payment of taxes or compliance with regulations.
- Illegal production: productive activities that generate goods and services forbidden by law or that are unlawful when carried out by unauthorized procedures. Informal sector production: productive activities conducted by unincorporated enterprises in the household sector or other units that are unregistered and/or less than a specified size in terms of employment, and that have some market production.
- Production of households for own-final use: productive activities that result in goods or services consumed or capitalized by the households that produced them.
- Statistical underground: defined as all productive activities that should be accounted for in basic data collection programs but are missed due to deficiencies in the statistical system.

In the “The Global Risks Report 2018” report, which was prepared by the World Economic Forum, information threats were included in the global risk rating. Threats such as “Cyber Attacks” and “Data

Theft and Fraud” are among the top five highly probable, a threat to critical infrastructures exists as well. There, the main areas of risk are highlighted: economic, geopolitical, environmental, social and technological. It is in the latter area that global transformations are focused, aimed at: information security, information technologies, Internet governance, digital economy and society, labor and employment, the future of economic progress, youth prospects, supplies and transport, migration, the 4th industrial revolution.

4. Analysis

The starting point of our study is “shadow IT” (Shadow IT, Stealth IT or Client IT). Various definitions are used, in particular:

- Shadow IT are all the third-party IT solutions, including cloud applications and services that are not controlled by the corporate IT department. Cloud solutions, which represent a large part of Shadow IT, can replace an employee function or an entire department, and become part of the enterprise services. Statistics of the actual use of cloud solutions in the corporate sector are amazing: there are hundreds of solutions, and not dozens, like many IT and information security experts believed. However, from a security point of view, cloud applications and services are a “blind spot”.
- Shadow IT refers to IT devices, software and services outside the ownership or control of IT organizations.
- Shadow IT represents all the hardware, software or any other solutions used by employees within the organizational ecosystem that have not received official approval from the IT department.
- Business units and users autonomously implement IT solutions that are not embedded in the organizational management of IT services. This increasingly growing phenomenon is called Shadow IT.
- Shadow IT is defined as a set of IT tools used to perform IT functions, but not part of the main IT organization.
- The authors define Shadow IT as any IT solution used by employees to perform their work tasks without the approval and official support of the IT department.
- For example, the so-called Shadow IT, that is, third-party IT solutions that are not controlled by corporate governance. And these are not always clouds, it can be any information systems that are out of sight or control. Shadow IT infrastructure is not always evil, it often arises from “good” motives to optimize legitimate business processes. Therefore, it must be identified and analyzed, and only if necessary, an alternative offered. This will help making the cloud environment controlled, convenient and secure [24].
- Shadow IT is a term used to describe the situation when business units acquire, own and manage IT resources without the help of an IT department. IT departments consider shadow IT as

inefficient as well as a source of risk and see part of their task as constraining its spread.

- Shadow IT is becoming increasingly important as digital methods of work simplify the work of business units creating their own IT solutions. Previous research on shadow IT systems often used fixed reports of good or evil: they were noted as powerful driving forces for innovation or demonized as missing central management. We present a method for IT managers and architects to enable a more subtle understanding of shadow IT systems with respect to their architectural embeddability.

- The term “shadow systems” refers to stand-alone software solutions or extensions of existing solutions that are not developed or controlled by the central IT department.

- Shadow IT refers to IT devices, software, and services that are present in the organization but are not serviced by the IT department. They are not registered with the IT department, their state and work are not monitored, moreover, the IT department may not know anything about them. Accordingly, security policies and regulations also do not apply to them. And this is a serious threat to corporate security. According to the forecast of Gartner, by 2020 a third of successful attacks on information resources of organizations will be performed through Shadow IT.

- Shadow IT is used to describe IT solutions and systems created and applied inside companies and organizations without their authorization. This is considered a vital foundation for technological advancement and innovation because these efforts can become potential prototypes for IT solutions that are approved in the future. Even though these solutions can help in the advancement of IT innovations, they may not conform to the company’s requirements in terms of reliability, documentation, control, security and more.

Even though these definitions touch upon very important points, in authors’ opinion, some of them lack the depth required to describe the phenomenon of SDE. The analysis of the abovementioned definitions of SDE allows us to identify five main approaches: legal, mathematical, socio-psychological, organizational and managerial, economic and financial.

- The legal approach describes this category from the perspective of legal science, focusing on illegal activities.

- Mathematical approach considers Shadow IT as a model of management of the shadow activity of participants in the information sector with the release of the life cycle of individual products and services, as well as monetization processes.

- The organizational and managerial approach is to determine SDE from the point of view of the organizational and legal form of interaction between participants in the shadow markets for products and services.

- Socio-psychological approach analyzes the activities of the participants in terms of irrational economic behavior, attracting a large number of specialists in information and communication technology.

- The economic and financial approach considers SDE as financial structures that launder money through the use of various frauds based on information and communication technologies in the legal market for goods and services.

Let us formulate the definition of the shadow digital economy, based on its specificity in terms of the production of goods and services, the life cycle of production and services, etc. Thus, SDE is a sector of economic relations that encompasses all types of production and business activities that, by their focus, content, nature, and form, are contrary to the requirements of legislation and are carried out contrary to state regulation of the economy and bypassing control over it. A generalized empirical model of SDE is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Empiric Model of SDE.

The basis of the SDE is the shadow business activity, the general features of which are as follows:

- hidden, latent (secret) character, meaning, the activity that is not registered by the state authorities and is not reflected in the official reporting;

- coverage of all phases of the process of social reproduction (production, distribution, exchange and consumption);

- the parasitic nature of all processes, ranging from the disclosure of the source code of a software product to the monetization of bot nets by renting.

A slightly different approach is used in the works of L. Gasparyniene, R. Remeikiene, F. Schneider [30-33], based on the processes of universal digitalization (digitalization) of the economy. In particular, the following definition of the shadow digital economy is proposed: “illegal activity in cyberspace, which allows generating illegal money flows for illegal service providers and vendors, as well as depriving incomes of legal service providers and vendors”

In our opinion, we should agree with the thesis proposed by F. Schneider in a joint article with A. Buen - researchers trying to measure the volume of the shadow economy face a basic and complex issue - to define this phenomenon. A general definition is used (the authors of the article call this definition a work in progress) - these are all types of unregistered activity that contributed to the gross national product. The proposed narrower definition of the shadow economy includes the following: The shadow economy includes all legally produced goods and services that are deliberately hidden from public authorities for the following reasons:

- Avoiding taxes (for example, income or value added tax).

- Avoiding social security contributions payments.
- Avoid using certain labor market standards, such as minimum wages, maximum working hours, safety standards, etc.
- Avoid adherence to certain administrative procedures.

Thus, SDE is all illegal and hidden goods and services that use and are based on information technology. The most important economic elements of this sphere are the following: illegal economic relations, illegal activities related to the production, distribution and use of prohibited products and services.

5. Discussion

Taking into account the main international documents agreed upon and adopted in 2018, relatively new directions of threats were identified. They are reflected in the following documents:

- "Developments in the field of information and telecommunications in the context of international security" Information Security Resolution, which was adopted by the UN on December 5, 2018;
- "The Paris Call for Trust and Security in Cyberspace", presented during the World Internet Governance Forum in Paris on November 12, 2018 (along with a speech by French President Emmanuel Macron);
- Recommendations of the Global Commission on Cyber Stability (Singapore Package, adopted in November 2018).

The following are outlined as the most topical threats:

- Personal data protection.
- Socially dangerous content (cyberbullying, calls for suicide).
- Interference in elections, attacks on electronic voting systems and information processing.
- Attacks on Internet of Things devices (industrial Internet).
- Attacks on electronic systems that serve the physical infrastructure of supplying various goods.

We consider it necessary to pay attention to the low level of knowledge of the following research areas: the possibility of implementing threats to medical equipment (in particular, in relation to cardiac pacemakers); cryptomania - as a socio-economic phenomenon; Wetware - computer technologies integrated with the biological organism; Digital Twin concept, etc.

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, we consider it possible to propose the development of an integrated strategy to counter the shadow information economy. The underlying principles of this strategy can be as follows:

- improvement of the legislative base of economic regulation, aimed at creating conditions under which the concealment of certain types of

activities or their elements, like any illegal activity, will be unprofitable;

- development of cooperation at the regional, state, and international levels in order to reduce the level of the shadow digital economy;
- creation of jobs, the reform of the tax system, with the aim of tightening measures against money laundering, as well as the stiffening of the struggle against corruption;
- improvement of education and training systems, improving the ability to resist the phenomenon of the shadow digital economy;
- expansion of the base of theoretical studies and practical developments aimed at new groups of threats, including Internet-related ones, aimed at medical equipment.

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